

Scientific Project

Effect of Dry Yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) and Soil Type on the Germination of Castor Seeds (*Ricinus communis*)

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Chapter One: Introduction

1.1 Research Background

Germination is one of the essential biological processes that marks the beginning of a plant's life cycle. It starts when the seed absorbs water, triggering a series of physiological changes leading to embryo growth. The success of germination heavily depends on environmental factors such as moisture, temperature, and oxygen, in addition to soil type and fertility.

Castor (*Ricinus communis*) is a plant of great economic importance, widely used in pharmaceutical and agricultural industries. Improving the germination conditions of castor seeds can significantly enhance production rates.

Dry yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*) serves as an active biological component that improves soil quality and boosts plant growth, making it an important topic of scientific research as a biofertilizer.

1.2 Research Importance

This study aims to explore the effects of different soil types and the use of dry yeast on the germination rate and hypocotyl length of castor seeds.

1.3 Research Questions

- What is the effect of soil type on the germination of castor seeds?
- What is the best soil type for optimal germination of castor seeds?
- To what extent does dry yeast enhance castor seed germination?

1.4 Research Objective

The primary objective is to identify the most suitable soil type for castor seed germination and to assess the impact of dry yeast on germination percentage and hypocotyl growth.

Chapter Two: Materials and Methodology

2.1 Study Area

The experiment was conducted in the science laboratory at Jerash Refugee Camp Girls' Preparatory School No. 1.

2.2 Materials Used

- 36 mature castor seeds.
- 6 different types of soil.
- Dry yeast (*Saccharomyces cerevisiae*).
- 36 planting containers.
- Water source for irrigation.
- Tools for measuring hypocotyl length.

2.3 Methodology

The containers were divided into two groups: with and without yeast addition. Seeds were soaked for 24 hours before planting, placed under controlled environmental conditions, and watered every two days.

Chapter Three: Results

3.1 Germination Rate without Yeast

Soil Type	Germination Rate	Start Period (Days)	Average Hypocotyl Length (cm)
Mukhayba	100%	7	11.63
Irbid	100%	8	10.5
School Soil	66.67%	9-10	11.6
Waqas	66.67%	11-13	1.45
Peat Moss	33.33%	10	-
Mafrq	0%	No Germination	0

3.2 Germination Rate with Yeast

Soil Type	Germination Rate with Yeast	Start Period (Days)	Average Hypocotyl Length (cm)
Mukhayba	100%	7	13.25
Irbid	100%	8	13.13
School Soil	33.33%	9-10	8.5
Waqas	66.67%	11-13	1.65
Peat Moss	33.33%	10	1.4
Mafrq	0%	No Germination	0

Chapter Four: Discussion

4.1 Analysis of Results

- Mukhayba and Irbid soils recorded the highest germination rates (100%) with and without yeast.
- The addition of yeast increased the hypocotyl length by 13.93% in Mukhayba and 25.04% in Irbid.
- School soil showed a decrease in germination rate with yeast.
- Mafraq soil showed no germination under any condition.

4.2 Study Limitations

Plants were initially exposed to cold conditions, negatively affecting growth, and requiring repetition of the experiment.

Chapter Five: Conclusion and Recommendations

5.1 Conclusion

Fertile soils such as Mukhayba and Irbid are optimal for castor seed germination, and yeast enhances growth in these soils.

5.2 Recommendations

- Expand research to different soils.
- Test the effect of yeast on various plants.
- Promote dry yeast as a sustainable biofertilizer.

Chapter Six: References

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